

In Silico Prediction of Genotoxicity: Current Applications and Future Perspectives

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Abstract

The use of in silico predictions for genotoxicity is common practice throughout the drug development pipeline, driven by the acceptance of mutagenicity predictions for regulatory assessment of impurities under ICH M7. Given their use in risk assessments of human health hazards, it is important to continue developing in silico tools to predict genotoxicity, improving the accuracy of models and expanding applicability more widely than mutagenicity. This talk will introduce tools currently used for the assessment of genotoxicity, primarily focused on mutagenicity under ICH M7. We will then consider emerging technologies to enable more accurate and interpretable predictions for other genotoxicity endpoints.